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Social Participation in the Italian Regions

Between 2005 and 2020 it decreased in all regions with the exception of Liguria

ISTAT calculates the value of social participation as part of the survey on Sustainable Equitable Wellbeing-BES. In particular, social participation is defined as: "People aged 14 and over who in the last 12 months have carried out at least one social participation activity out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The activities considered are: participation in meetings of associations (cultural / recreational, ecological, civil rights, for peace); participated in meetings of trade union organizations, professional or trade associations; attended meetings of political parties and / or carried out free activity for a party; pay a monthly or periodic fee for a sports club / club".

The ranking of the regions by value of social participation in 2020. Trentino-Alto Adige is in first post by value of social participation in 2020 with a value of 34.2, followed by Veneto with an amount of 27.3 and by Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount equal to 27.2. In the middle of the table there are Liguria with an amount equal to 23.7, followed by Valle D'Aosta with an amount equal to 23.6 and Piedmont with a value equal to 23. Campania closes the ranking with an amount equal to 15.3, Sicily with a value of 14.7 and Calabria with a value of 13.1.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in social participation between 2005 and 2020. Liguria is in first place for percentage change in social participation between 2005 and 2020 with a value of +17.33% equivalent to an amount of +3.5 points in absolute value, followed by Molise with a value equal to -4.62% equal to -1 units in absolute value, and by Umbria with a value equal to -6.59% equal to -1, 7 units. In the middle of the table there are Tuscany with a value equal to -12.95% or equal to -3.6 units, followed by Basilicata with a value equal to -13.22% equal to -3 units, and by Friuli-Venezia Giulia with a value equal to -13.38% equal to -4.2 units. Trentino-Alto Adige closes the ranking with an amount equal to -23.15% equal to -10.3 units, followed by the Marche with a value equal to -28.36% equal to -7.8 units and Calabria with a value equal to -36.41% equal to -7.5 units. Between 2005 and 2020 the value of the shareholding in the 20 Italian regions decreased by an amount equal to -13.96% or by a value equal to -3.81 units.

North. The value of the shareholding in Northern Italy decreased in the period between 2016 and 2020. In 2016 the value of the shareholding was equal to an amount of 28 units and passed to a value of 26.30 units in 2017 with a change equal to a value of -1.70 units equal to -6.07%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018 the value of the shareholding in Northern Italy went from an amount equal to 26.30 units up to a value equal to 27.40 units or equal to a value of 1.10 units equal to a value of 4.18%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019 the value of the shareholding decreased from an amount of 27.40 to a value of 25.60 or a change of -1.80 units equal to -6.57%. In the transition

between 2019 and 2020 the value of the shareholding in Northern Italy decreased from an amount equal to 25.60 to a value of 25.50 units or a reduction of -0.10 units equal to -0.39 %. Overall, in the period between 2016 and 2020 the value of the shareholding in the Italian macro-regions decreased by an amount equal to 2.50 units equal to -8.93%.

Center. The value of the shareholding in Central Italy decreased in the period between 2016 and 2020 from an amount equal to 26.50 up to an amount equal to 23.90 or a reduction equal to -2.60 units equal to a value of -9.81%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the shareholding decreased from an amount equal to 26.50 units up to a value equal to 24.30 units or equal to a value of -2.20 units equal to -8, 30%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018 the value of the shareholding in Central Italy increased from an amount equal to 24.30 up to a value of 25.20 or equal to an amount of 0.90 units equal to 3.70% . Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the shareholding in Central Italy decreased from an amount equal to 25.20 units up to a value equal to 23.80 units or equal to a change of -1.40 units equal to -5 , 56%. In the transition between 2019 and 2020, the value of the shareholding in Central Italy increased from an amount of 23.80 units up to a value of 23.90 units or equal to a change of 0.10 units equal to an amount of -6.08%.

South of Italy. The value of the shareholding decreased in the South between 2016 and 2020 from an amount equal to 17.50 units up to a value equal to 17.00 units or equal to a variation of 2.86%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of the shareholding in the Mezzogiorno decreased from an amount equal to 17.50 units to a value of 17.20 units or equal to a variation of -0.30 units equivalent to a value of -1.71%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the shareholding increased from a value of 17.20 units to a value of 18.60 units or equal to a change of 1.40 units equal to an amount of 8 , 14%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019, the value of the shareholding in the Mezzogiorno decreased from an amount equal to 18.60 units up to a value equal to 18.10 units or equal to a change of -0.50 units equal to a value of -2.69%. In the transition between 2019 and 2020 the value of the shareholding in the South has decreased from an amount of 18.10 units up to a value equal to 17.00 units or equal to a value of -1.10 units or equal to a value of -6.08%.

Clusterization. Clustering is proposed below using the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient to verify the presence of groupings between the Italian regions that may in some way reverberate the structure of the Italian macro-regions. There are three clusters as indicated below:

- *Cluster 1:* Tuscany, Emilia-Romagna, Lombardy, Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta, Umbria, Marche, Sardinia, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Veneto, Abruzzo, Liguria, Basilicata;
- *Cluster 2:* Trentino-Alto Adige;
- *Cluster 3:* Calabria, Sicily, Campania, Puglia, Molise.

In particular, it appears that the value of the median of the social participation in Cluster 2 is equal to 34.2, the value of the median of the social participation in Cluster 1 is equal to 23.9 and the value of the social participation in Cluster 3 is equal to 15. , 3. Therefore, it appears that the ordering of the clusters consists of C2> C1> C3. It is evident that the Center-North has a very large value of social participation, with a peak of values in Trentino-Alto Adige, while the South, with the exclusion of Sardinia, Abruzzo and Basilicata, appears to have very bass.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Predictions are made below using eight different machine learning algorithms. The algorithms were trained using 70% of the analyzed data while the remaining 30% was used for prediction. The algorithms have been organized based on their ability to optimize four different types of statistical errors, namely: "Mean Absolute Error", "Mean Squared Error",

"Root Mean Squared Error", "Mean Signed Difference". Therefore, the following ordering of the algorithms derives from it, with indication of the relative payoff, that is:

- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 4;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 8;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a value of 12;
- PNN - Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 16;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 20;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 24;
- Gradient Boosted Tree Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 32.

It follows that Tree Ensemble Regression is the best predictor. Through the use of the Tree Ensemble Regression value, the following values are predicted:

- Valle d'Aosta with a variation from an amount equal to 23.6 up to a value of 25.34 or a variation of +1.74 units or equal to a value of + 7.37%;
- Lombardia with a variation from an amount of 24.3 units up to a value equal to 23.68 or equal to a variation of -0.62 units or equal to an amount of -2.54%;
- Veneto with a variation from an amount equal to 27.3 units up to an amount of 26.91 units or equal to a variation of -0.39 units equal to -1.44%;
- Tuscany with a variation from an amount equal to 24.2 units up to an amount of 23.89 units or equal to a variation of -0.31 units equal to -1.29%;
- Marche or a change from an amount equal to 19.7 units up to a value of 23.18 units or equal to a change of 3.48 units or equal to a value of 17.68%;
- Puglia with a diminutive variation with a variation from an amount of 20 units up to a value of 16.48 units or a variation equal to -3.52 units equal to -17.60%.

On average, as shown by the prediction, the value of the social participation for the regions analyzed is predicted to grow in the medina by an absolute value of 0.06 units or equal to a percentage value of 0.36.

Conclusions. In summary, we can verify that the value of social participation in the Italian regions has substantially decreased in all regions. However, between 2005 and 2020 the value of social participation decreased in all Italian macro-regions with a value equal to -17.7% in the North, -13.4% in the Center, and equal to -17% in the Noon. It clearly follows that approximately 77.7% of the Italian over-14 population lacks social participation. The value of the share capital was significantly eroded between 2005 and 2020 in the various Italian regions, except for Liguria, the only Italian region with an increase in the value of shareholding. Since share capital is a significant determinant of economic growth, it follows that this compression of share capital is a harbinger of a further slowdown of the Italian economy in terms of creating added value.

Partecipazione Sociale 2005-2020. Variazione Percentuale. Istat-BES

Valore della Partecipazione Sociale nelle Macro-Regioni Italiane. Fonte: ISTAT-BES

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2016-2020
Nord	★ 28,00	★ 26,30	★ 27,40	★ 25,60	★ 25,50	
Variazione assoluta		☆ -1,70	☆ 1,10	☆ -1,80	☆ -0,10	☆ -2,50
Variazione percentuale		☆ -6,07	★ 4,18	☆ -6,57	☆ -0,39	☆ -8,93
Centro	★ 26,50	★ 24,30	★ 25,20	★ 23,80	★ 23,90	
Variazione assoluta		☆ -2,20	☆ 0,90	☆ -1,40	☆ 0,10	☆ -2,60
Variazione percentuale		☆ -8,30	★ 3,70	☆ -5,56	☆ 0,42	☆ -9,81
Mezzogiorno	★ 17,50	★ 17,20	★ 18,60	★ 18,10	★ 17,00	
Variazione assoluta		☆ -0,30	☆ 1,40	☆ -0,50	☆ -1,10	☆ -0,50
Variazione percentuale		☆ -1,71	★ 8,14	☆ -2,69	☆ -6,08	☆ -2,86
Italia	★ 24,10	★ 22,80	★ 23,90	★ 22,70	★ 22,30	
Variazione assoluta		☆ -1,30	☆ 1,10	☆ -1,20	☆ -0,40	☆ -1,80
Variazione percentuale		☆ -5,39	★ 4,82	☆ -5,02	☆ -1,76	☆ -7,47

Valore della Partecipazione Sociale nelle Macro-Regioni Italiane. Fonte: ISTAT-BES

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
■ Nord	28,00	26,30	27,40	25,60	25,50
■ Centro	26,50	24,30	25,20	23,80	23,90
■ Mezzogiorno	17,50	17,20	18,60	18,10	17,00

Partecipazione Sociale nelle Regioni Italiane nel 2020					
Rank	Regione	2020	Rank	Regione	2020
1	Trentino-Alto Adige	★ 34,2	11	Piemonte	★ 23
2	Veneto	★ 27,3	12	Abruzzo	★ 21,9
3	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 27,2	13	Sardegna	★ 20,8
4	Emilia-Romagna	★ 26,5	14	Molise	★ 20,6
5	Lazio	★ 24,8	15	Puglia	★ 20
6	Lombardia	★ 24,3	16	Marche	★ 19,7
7	Toscana	★ 24,2	17	Basilicata	★ 19,7
8	Umbria	★ 24,1	18	Campania	★ 15,3
9	Liguria	★ 23,7	19	Sicilia	★ 14,7
10	Valle d'Aosta	★ 23,6	20	Calabria	★ 13,1

Partecipazione Sociale nelle Regioni Italiane nel 2020

Partecipazione Sociale 2005-2020. Istat-BES

Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var %
1	Liguria	★ 3,5	★ 17,33
2	Molise	★ -1	★ -4,63
3	Umbria	★ -1,7	★ -6,59
4	Puglia	★ -1,5	★ -6,98
5	Emilia-Romagna	★ -2,7	★ -9,25
6	Lazio	★ -3	★ -10,79
7	Lombardia	★ -3	★ -10,99
8	Sicilia	★ -2,1	★ -12,50
9	Toscana	★ -3,6	★ -12,95
10	Basilicata	★ -3	★ -13,22
11	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ -4,2	★ -13,38
12	Sardegna	★ -3,6	★ -14,75
13	Veneto	★ -5,2	★ -16,00
14	Piemonte	★ -4,5	★ -16,36
15	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ -5,1	★ -17,77
16	Abruzzo	★ -5,4	★ -19,78
17	Campania	★ -4,5	★ -22,73
18	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	★ -10,3	★ -23,15
19	Marche	★ -7,8	★ -28,36
20	Calabria	★ -7,5	★ -36,41
	Media	-3,81	-13,96